

Implementation of the Flipped Classroom Model Using Mobile Learning at UPG 1945 NTT

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Abstract- The problem of learning English at the Teacher's Union University (UPG) 1945 NTT Kupang is that the ability of students to master and understand English is quite difficult both reading, writing, listening and oral, because the learning system applied is centered on the lecturer as a teacher. This results in one-way and non-interactive learning because students only passively listen to lecturers' explanations, do not focus / fantasize in learning, and do not actively respond to learning materials presented by lecturers so that students find it difficult to construct creative and innovative ideas to understand English subject matter independently. . The purpose of this study is to apply the flipped classroom learning model using a mobile learning application in learning English courses at UPG NTT. The research method uses the waterfall which includes 5 stages, namely identification of user needs, analysis, design, implementation, and testing. The result of the research is that UPG 1945 NTT Kupang students use mobile learning applications in learning English as a flipped classroom learning model to improve the quality of education and the achievement of student competence in learning. The application of the flipped classroom learning model using a mobile learning application changes the way students learn from lecturer-centered learning to student-centered learning. The outputs targeted in this research are mandatory outputs in the form of international journal articles, additional outputs in the form of ISBN books published by IKAPI member publishers, and this research produces a prototype product for an Android-based mobile learning application as a learning media for the flipped classroom model.

Keywords: Mobile learning, flipped classroom, English language, Application

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of information technology as an innovation of learning media in the world of education has begun to be applied on campuses on the island of Java. especially in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 which is oriented towards the advancement of digital technology such as the use of smart phones in learning. The 1945 University of the Teacher Association NTT Kupang (UPG 1945 NTT) has a faculty of teaching and education that oversees the English language department as one of the majors that has quite a lot of enthusiasts (students). The problem is that the ability of students to master and understand English courses is quite difficult both reading, writing, listening and oral, because the learning system / semester learning plan (RPS) applied at UPG 1945 NTT is centered on the lecturer as a teacher. This results in one-way and non-interactive learning because students only passively listen to the lecturer's explanations, do not focus / fantasize in learning, do not actively respond to the learning material presented by the lecturer, do not ask questions because they are ashamed to be considered stupid, and so on, so that students find it difficult to construct ideas. creative and innovative ideas to understand English subject matter independently. Another problem in learning English at UPG is the number of meetings per week and the limited length of study according to the lecture schedule which causes the English subject matter to be incomplete which has an impact on improving the quality of education and competency achievement for students. These problems inspired the research team to propose innovative smart solutions through the application of the flipped classroom model using mobile learning

as a sustainable advanced technology in the increasingly sophisticated and rapidly developing digital era. The research conducted by Kuntum and Siti (2020) aims to create a Mobile Learning development with the Flipped Classroom model to facilitate learning activities to be more effective & efficient in accordance with learning rules and oriented to the goals to be achieved in learning. Mobile Learning with the Flipped Classroom model can be accessed by students more flexibly without being limited by space and time, effectively and efficiently in the implementation of learning. Hanifudin Sukri and Doni Abdul Fatah (2020) explained that the current millennial generation student learning method has used mobile phone media which offers more reference models such as videos, simulations, and so on. The conventional learning model that relies on lecturers or Teacher Centered Learning (TCL) is replaced with Student Centered Learning (SCL). The application of appropriate learning strategies and methods in accordance with the times and technology will increase the effectiveness of student learning and can increase students' independent learning power, with the Flipped Classroom method, which is usually given in class and students do assignments at home. The Flipped Classroom concept includes active learning, student engagement, and podcasting, the material is first given through learning videos that students must watch at home. On the other hand, classroom learning sessions are used for group discussions, discussions with lecturers about material that is difficult to understand during independent study and doing assignments. The specific purpose of the research that the team proposes is to apply the flipped classroom learning model using a mobile learning application in learning English courses at UPG NTT so as to improve the quality of education and the achievement of student competence in learning. The application of the flipped classroom learning model using a mobile learning application changes the way students learn from lecturer-centered learning to student-centered learning. Flipped classroom is one way of learning where students get learning materials, exercises, assignments, and exams in the form of text, video, animation, or in the form of interactive multimedia that is distributed and accessed by students online whenever and wherever students are using mobile learning applications. android based. English course materials, exercises, assignments, and exams in digital form are done outside the classroom to be discussed during the course hours. So when in class, what the teacher

does is to review material, discuss assignments or exercises, and answer questions from students who still don't understand the material that has been distributed online. Meanwhile, students who come to class are expected to understand the English material given by the lecturer because it has been studied repeatedly (digital material) outside the classroom whenever and wherever students are. The application of the flipped classroom model using a mobile learning application can improve the quality of education, achievement of learning competencies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The teaching-learning process for English courses that are running at the University of the Teacher's Association (UPG) 1945 NTT Kupang is still traditional / classical, namely the lecturer delivers subject matter only in the classroom so that learning activities are not optimal because time is limited according to the course schedule. semester. Traditional or face-to-face learning brings together lecturers and students in one room to study where the lecturer delivers lecture material orally or orally and students listen, take notes, ask questions, discuss, and are evaluated. So far, lecturers teach English subject matter only using book media, explain subject matter on the blackboard, give homework to students and provide subject matter in the form of power points. The traditional learning model for English courses at UPG 1945 NTT which is centered on lecturers/teachers needs to be changed to a student-centered learning model to improve the quality of education and the achievement of learning competencies. The industrial revolution 4.0 has changed various human activities that are operated automatically and digitally. Likewise in the educational environment that needs to keep up with advances in Information and Communication technology to change various learning models to be innovative and interactive with the support of various learning media and computer-based learning applications or smart phones. When we are in an unavoidable digital world, it is not surprising that there is growing interest related to learning technology using mobile learning. The application of learning technology using mobile phone media needs to be supported by appropriate learning methods or models such as the flipped classroom learning model. Flipped classroom proposes that students learn through interactive technology such as watching videos at home and preparing themselves to apply

active learning strategies. So that teachers can spend time with students who need help in class and students can work together to solve problems or discuss in class instead of just sitting still and doing assignments on their own that may not be understood and no one can help. Basically, the concept of Flipped Classroom is that learning that takes place in class becomes learning that is done at home, and homework or assignments that should be done at home, will be completed in class. Flipped classroom is active learning, with a student-centered approach that can improve the quality of learning during class. Flipped Classroom learning emphasizes more on the use of time inside and outside the classroom so that learning is of higher quality so that it can improve students' understanding of the material (Abeysekera 2015). The types of flipped classroom according to Utami (2017) are traditional flipped, Mastery flipped, Peer Instruction flipped, and Problem based learning flipped. Mobile Learning is a learning model that utilizes information and communication technology. In this learning concept, mobile learning brings the benefits of the availability of teaching materials that can be accessed at any time, effectively, and the visualization of interesting material (Quin 2010). According to Masfufah (2015) and Wijaya (2015) explain that Mobile Learning has characters that are relevant to the progress of the times. Mobile Learning makes life easier or the world of learning that exists if we observe in terms of its characteristics. Kumar, et al (2013) stated that the use of mobile phones is increasing which is changing the way of working and learning. This can facilitate students to access learning resources without the need to be physically present in the classroom. The advantages of using mobile learning are increased mobility which allows students to access learning content wherever they are, time and cost efficiency for the teaching and learning process, learning media is easy to carry anywhere they go, and students can interact with teachers or classmates (Santosh 2013).

3. METHOD

The application of the flipped classroom learning model using mobile learning applications in learning English courses at UPG 1945 NTT Kupang uses the waterfall method which includes five stages, namely: (1) identification of the needs of the flipped classroom, (2) analysis of the needs of the flipped classroom model, (3) design mobile

learning learning media, (4) the implementation of the flipped classroom model using mobile learning, and (5) testing the application of the flipped classroom learning model using a mobile learning application. The following figure shows the flipped classroom learning development method using a mobile learning application.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research carried out in July 2021 by the head of the research team who carried out learning English courses in classrooms at the University of 45 NTT as shown in Figure 1. The learning model is more centered on the lecturer / teacher who explains the learning material in the classroom. class so that it is difficult for students to increase learning independence and trigger student creativity in managing the learning process.

Figure 1. Teaching and Learning Process at 45 NTT University in Classroom

The application of the flipped classroom learning model using a mobile learning application changes the way students learn from lecturer-centered learning to student-centered learning. Flipped classroom is one way of learning where students get learning materials, exercises, assignments, and exams in the form of text, video, animation, or in the form of interactive multimedia that is distributed and accessed by students online whenever and wherever students are using mobile learning applications. android based. English course materials, exercises, assignments, and exams in digital form are done outside the classroom to be discussed during the course hours. So when in class, what the teacher does is to review material, discuss assignments or exercises, and answer questions from students who still don't understand the material that has been distributed online. Meanwhile, students who come to class are expected to understand the English material given by the lecturer because it has been studied repeatedly (digital material) outside the classroom whenever and wherever students are. Learning to use a mobile phone or smartphone owned by each student is not only used for social media services (facebook, instagram, twitter), playing games, watching videos, reading messages, etc. interesting and students

can study wherever and whenever they want. Based on the research stages (application development methods) as planned in the proposal, the results of the research are the development of mobile phone-based English vocabulary learning applications that can improve English mastery for UPG 1945 NTT Kupang students. This can increase students' motivation and interest in learning English, which is student-centered, triggers student creativity, effectiveness, builds student independence in learning English, and the teaching and learning process can be done whenever and wherever students want to learn. The mobile phone-based English flipped classroom learning application has 11 service menus, namely registration, login, home, module 1 Wh-Questions, module 2 Modals, module 3 Introductory, module 4 Singular Forms, module 5 To be, going to, and Will, module 6 Reading Comprehension, module 7 Tag-Questions, and module 8 Degree of Comparison. Analysis and design of functional and operational requirements of an English flipped classroom mobile learning application which is modeled using Use case diagrams and activity diagrams.

Figure 2. Use Case Diagram of English Flipped Classroom Mobile Application

Figure 3. Activity Diagram of the English Flipped Classroom Mobile Application

The display of the English flipped classroom mobile application program is shown in Figures 4 and 5 below.

Figure 4. Main Menu of Flipped Classroom Mobile Application

Figure 5. Display of Mobile Flipped Classroom Learning Materials

5. CONCLUSION

The result of the research is that UPG 1945 NTT Kupang students use mobile learning applications in learning English as a flipped classroom learning model to improve the quality of education and the achievement of student competence in learning. The application of the flipped classroom learning model using a mobile learning application changes the way students learn from lecturer-centered learning to student-centered learning.

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